

The Impact of International Agreements on Indigenous People In Indonesia

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Abstract

Inter-state relations and interdependence, whether economic, political, defence, etc., are essential for the welfare of the citizens of a state. The implementation of inter-state relations is done by using international agreements between a country and other countries or international organisations and must be subject to international law. Foreign investment has a great influence on the economic growth of a country and is a determinant factor for the growth and welfare of the society. However, with respect to foreign investment issues, indigenous and tribal peoples are marginalized when dealing with rulers as well as foreign businessmen (foreign investors). As a result, the opportunity for indigenous peoples to participate in public decisions on economic, socio-cultural and political issues that affect their existence is limited. Nonetheless, law enforcement and investment policies should be aimed at financing the development and welfare of the people, and foreign investments should only be viewed as a complement and should neither be allowed to cause disharmony nor harm the rights of citizens and the national interests.

Keywords: International Agreements; Indigenous People

Introduction

The Government of Indonesia in exercising its foreign policy has always made efforts to fight for its national interests. It attempts to achieve this, among other ways, by reaching international agreements with other countries and international organisations, and such agreements must be subject to law. International agreements are the main instruments for the implementation of international relations between countries. International agreements have several terms or names, such as convention, final act, declaration, memorandum of understanding (MOU), agreement, protocol, etc. These terms are mere names with no juridical effect. Increasing the intensity of relations and inter-state independence lead to increased international cooperation as outlined in various international treaties.

According to Article 2 of the Vienna Convention of 1969 on the Law of Treaties, an international treaty is an agreement made between states in written form and governed by international law, whether it consists of one or more instruments and whatever its name. The Vienna Convention of 1969 is only used in disputes concerning treaties established between states, and such treaties must be in written form. For disputes involving non-state parties, for example international organisations, the arrangements are defined in the Vienna Convention of 1986 on the Law of Treaties between States and International Organisations or between International Organisations. An important requirement for an agreement to be regarded as an international treaty is that the treaty is subject to the international legal regime even though its parties are states (Himahanto Juwana; 2010: 16).

International agreements in Indonesia are regulated by Law Number 24 Year 2000 on International Agreements. According to Law No. 24 Year 2000, international agreements are agreements in certain forms and names, subject to international laws, made in writing as well as incurring rights and obligations in the field of public law. Also, Regional Autonomy Law Number 24 Year 2000 gives regional authorities the authority to enter into international agreements, as regulated in Article 5 of Law Number 24 Year 2000. International agreements may take the form of bilateral, trilateral, regional, multilateral or global agreements, based on the number of participants (Selfriani; 2016:7).

Based on law, international treaties can be differentiated into treaty contract and law making treaty. A treaty contract is a closed agreement that does not give opportunity to a party who did not participate in the negotiation to become a participant in the agreement. Treaty contracts exist as bilateral, trilateral, and regional agreements, for example the border agreement between Indonesia and Malaysia. Law making treaties are agreements that create legal principles that are not only binding on the participants of the agreement but can also be binding on a third party. Law making treaties are commonly found in open, multilateral agreements. This type of agreement is a codification of customary law that is already applicable and contains progressive development in international law accepted as customary law or as a universal law principle, for example the Vienna Convention of 1961 on Diplomatic Relations.

Some important principles in international treaty law are as follows:

1. Voluntary: no party shall be bound by a treaty through any of the recognised means, such as signing, ratifying or accessing, without his consent.
2. *Pacta Sunt Servanda*: binding treaties are like laws for the parties.
3. *Pacta tertiis nec nocent nec prosunt*: the agreement does not grant rights and obligations to third parties without their consent.

4. When all the articles of a treaty constitute a custom codification of international customary law, the entire contents of the treaty shall be binding on all international societies, including those who do not ratify it; a state that has not ratified it is bound not by its covenant but because of its international customary law.
5. If a treaty is a mix between customary law and progressive development, the participating countries shall be bound by the whole of the treaty; the non-participating countries shall be bound only by the contents of the treaty that are a codification of customary law; and the non-participating states may also be bound by the provisions that are related to progressive development when the progressive development has become a new customary law

The authority of the government of Indonesia to enter into international agreements is contained in Article 11 of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia (UD NKRI 1945), which states as follows: The President has the authority to enter into international agreements with the approval of the People's Legislative Assembly. The creation and ratification of international agreements between the Indonesian government and the governments of other countries and international organisations according to international law is a very important legal act, since it binds the state to other international legal regimes. Therefore, making and validating an international agreement is based on law (Himahanto Juwana; 2010: 30).

The signing of a treaty shall not necessarily be interpreted as binding on the parties to the treaty. The signing of an international agreement requires approval to be binding. The treaty shall not be binding on the parties unless the agreement is ratified. Approval of international treaties by the government shall be done as long as it is required by the treaty. The ratification of an international agreement shall be done on the basis of the provisions agreed upon by the parties. International agreements requiring ratification shall enter into force upon the fulfillment of the legal procedures stipulated by law.

Through international agreements, each country outlines the basis of cooperation, organises various activities, and solves various problems for the sake of community survival. In addition, international agreements also serve as a means to enhance international cooperation, which ultimately is expected to improve the welfare and prosperity of the people. In reality, however, agreements made with governments of other countries, for example in the investment sector, often result in conflict/dispute between the government and indigenous peoples because of the investments made in indigenous peoples' territories. These conflicts occur due to

indigenous peoples' rights over customary land / ulayat land, which ultimately limits access to natural resources.

The issues affecting indigenous peoples are regulated at the international and national levels. At the international level, there is the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, which provides international arrangements to safeguard the basic rights of indigenous and tribal peoples and to promote peace and good relations between each group and the state. Article 2 of the declaration states that indigenous peoples and individuals should be free from all forms of discrimination in exercising their rights. It should be recognised that indigenous and tribal peoples are a group of people who recognise themselves as different from other people, and this distinction must be respected. The declaration takes into account the rights of indigenous peoples existing in the world to freely practise the activities they are known for.

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